

Detecting Target Motion by Frequency-Plane Smoothing

Jeffery C. Allen
Code 575, NRaD
San Diego, CA 92152-5000

Stephen L. Hobbs
Code 733, NRaD
San Diego, CA 92152-5000

Abstract

The technique of "diagonal smoothing" provides a consistent estimator of the two-dimensional spectrum for a harmonizable, periodically-correlated random process. This technique is extended to "radial" and "Doppler" smoothing to produce consistent estimators for the two-dimensional cross-spectrum of sensor outputs receiving a signal from a moving target.

1 Introduction

If $\{x(t)\}$ and $\{y(t)\}$ denote the output of two sensors which receive a signal $\{s(t)\}$ generated by a moving target in a noisy environment then the linear motion model (LMM) is:

$$\text{LMM} : \begin{cases} x(t) = s(\alpha t - \tau_1) + u(t) \\ y(t) = s(\beta t - \tau_2) + v(t) \end{cases},$$

where $\{u(t)\}$ and $\{v(t)\}$ denote the sensor noise. Even in the case when $\{s(t)\}$ is wide-sense stationary (WSS), the target motion can induce non-stationary structure. However, consistent estimation of the 2D cross-spectrum is possible. Indeed, the diagonal smoothing technique used to estimate the spectrum for a periodically correlated (PC) process can be generalized when $\{s(t)\}$ is WSS or PC. Coherent collapse of the 2D spectrum permits estimates of the time delay and time scaling parameters.

Section 2 reviews harmonizable and PC processes and the diagonal smoothing technique used to estimate the spectrum of a PC process. Section 3 adapts the diagonal smoothing to estimate the cross-spectrum of the linear motion model when $\{s(t)\}$ is WSS. Section 4 adapts the diagonal smoothing to estimate the cross-spectrum of the linear motion model when $\{s(t)\}$ is PC. Section 5 illustrates radial and Doppler smoothing on synthetic time series. The remainder of this introduction sets notation.

Throughout this paper we will assume all random processes are zero mean. The cross-covariance function of the random processes $\{x(t)\}$ and $\{y(t)\}$ is denoted as:

$$R_{xy}(t_1, t_2) = E[x(t_1)y(t_2)^H],$$

where the superscript H denotes the conjugate transpose. If the covariance $R_{xx}(t_1, t_2)$ of $\{x(t)\}$ depends only on the lag $t_1 - t_2$ then $\{x(t)\}$ is said to be wide-sense stationary (WSS). If the cross-covariance $R_{xy}(t_1, t_2)$ depends only on the lag $t_1 - t_2$, then $\{x(t)\}$

and $\{y(t)\}$ are said to be jointly WSS. The cross-spectrum of $\{x(t)\}$ and $\{y(t)\}$ is defined:

$$S_{xy}(f_1, f_2) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-i2\pi(f_1 t_1 - f_2 t_2)} R_{xy}(t_1, t_2) dt_1 dt_2.$$

We make the assumption that R_{xy} is a tempered distribution so that its Fourier transform is well-defined. When $\{x(t)\}$ and $\{y(t)\}$ are jointly WSS, their cross-power spectrum is

$$P_{xy}(f) = \hat{R}_{xy}(f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-i2\pi f t} R_{xy}(\tau) d\tau.$$

The relation between the spectrum and the power spectrum for a WSS processes $\{x(t)\}$ is

$$S_{xx}(f_1, f_2) = P_{xx}(f_1)\delta(f_1 - f_2).$$

2 Harmonizable Processes, PC Processes, and Diagonal Smoothing

An important class of non-stationary random processes are those which are Fourier transforms of random measures.

Definition 2.1 [7, page 474] A random process $\{x(t)\}$ is called (strongly) harmonizable provided it can be represented in quadratic mean for every $t \in \mathbf{R}$ by the integral

$$x(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{+i2\pi f t} dX(f)$$

where X is a random measure for which the set function defined on rectangles $A \times B$ as $S_{xx}(A \times B) = E[X(A)X(B)^H]$ extends to a measure of bounded variation in the plane $\mathbf{R} \times \mathbf{R}$.

Harmonizable processes subsume a variety of nonstationary random processes. Indeed, Hurd [2] obtains a sufficient condition for Priestley's oscillatory processes to be harmonizable. An important class of harmonizable process are those which are also PC.

Definition 2.2 [8, page 226] A random process $\{x(t)\}$ is called periodically correlated (PC) of period $T > 0$ provided the mean and covariance functions are periodic: for all $t \in \mathbf{R}$, there holds $E[x(t+T)] = E[x(t)]$ and for all $t_1, t_2 \in \mathbf{R}$, there holds $R_{xx}(t_1, t_2) = R_{xx}(t_1 + T, t_2 + T)$.

Hurd [3] points out that when $\{x(t)\}$ is both PC and harmonizable then the spectrum S_{xx} is supported on diagonal lines in the frequency plane spaced $1/T$ Hertz apart. More formally, the spectrum has the form

$$S_{xx}(f_1, f_2) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} S_k(f_1) \delta(f_1 - f_2 - k/T).$$

A key result for PC processes is that Hurd [4] demonstrated that a consistent estimator of S_{xx} can be obtained through "diagonal smoothing" of the two-dimensional periodogram of a single record of these kinds of processes. Thus, even though the process is non-stationary, the spectrum is amenable to estimation. Theorem 2.1 illustrates these points. We remark that Hurd and Leskow [6] have obtained a similar result under much more general assumptions but only estimate the spectrum along lines of spectral support. Our theorem uses more specialized assumptions but demonstrates consistent estimation for the entire plane.

Theorem 2.1 Let $\{x(t)\}$ be a strongly harmonizable PC process with period T . Make the following assumptions: $\{x(t)\}$ is real-valued and Gaussian; $\{x(t)\}$ is bandlimited; $S_k \in L^1(\mathbf{R})$ and $\widehat{S}_k \in L^1(\mathbf{R})$ for all integers k . Let the finite Fourier transform of the sample be denoted

$$\widehat{x}(b; f) = \int_{-b}^b e^{-i2\pi f t} x(t) dt.$$

Let the "raw" spectrum be defined as

$$S_{xx}(b; f_1, f_2) = \frac{1}{2b} \widehat{x}(b; f_1) \widehat{x}(b; f_2)^H.$$

Consider diagonally smoothing the raw spectrum:

$$S_{xx}(b, \epsilon; f_1, f_2) = \frac{1}{2\epsilon} \int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} S_{xx}(b; f_1 + f, f_2 + f) df$$

Then for each (f_1, f_2) in the frequency plane:

$$\lim_{\substack{b \rightarrow \infty \\ \epsilon \rightarrow 0}} S_{xx}(b, \epsilon; f_1, f_2) = \begin{cases} S_k(f_1) & f_1 - f_2 = k/T \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

in quadratic mean, provided $b\epsilon \rightarrow \infty$.

3 Radial Smoothing

Theorem 3.1 Assume the sensor outputs $\{x(t)\}$ and $\{y(t)\}$ are generated by the linear motion model (LMM). Assume signal $\{s(t)\}$ is WSS and uncorrelated with the WSS noise processes $\{u(t)\}$ and $\{v(t)\}$. Assume also that both noise processes are jointly uncorrelated. Then the sensor outputs $\{x(t)\}$ and $\{y(t)\}$ are WSS but not jointly WSS, and have cross spectrum:

$$S_{xy}(f_1, f_2) = \frac{1}{\alpha\beta} e^{-i2\pi\{\alpha^{-1}f_1\tau_1 - \beta^{-1}f_2\tau_2\}} \times P_{ss}(\alpha^{-1}f_1) \delta(\alpha^{-1}f_1 - \beta^{-1}f_2)$$

Figure 1 illustrates the support of the cross-spectrum of Theorem 3.1 and suggests estimating the cross spectrum by smoothing the "raw" cross spectrum $S_{xy}(b; f_1, f_2)$ using radial line segments:

$$S_{xy}^{(r)}(b, \epsilon; f_1, f_2) = \int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} S_{xy}(b; f_1 + f \cos(\theta), f_2 + f \sin(\theta)) df,$$

where $\tan(\theta) = f_2/f_1$. This estimation procedure will be called "radial smoothing" and yields a consistent estimation scheme.

Theorem 3.2 Assume the sensor outputs $\{x(t)\}$ and $\{y(t)\}$ are generated by the linear motion model (LMM) for a WSS signal $\{s(t)\}$ in WSS noise. Assume $\{s(t)\}$ is real-valued and Gaussian and uncorrelated with the noise processes. Assume both noise processes are jointly uncorrelated and $R_{ss}, R_{uu}, R_{vv} \in L^1(\mathbf{R})$. If $0 < \alpha < \beta$ and f_1, f_2 strictly positive, then

$$\lim_{\substack{b \rightarrow \infty \\ \epsilon \rightarrow 0}} S_{xy}^{(r)}(b, \epsilon; f_1, f_2) = \begin{cases} \beta^{-1} e^{-i2\pi\alpha^{-1}f_1(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} P_{ss}(\alpha^{-1}f_1) & \alpha f_2 = \beta f_1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

in quadratic mean, provided $b\epsilon \rightarrow \infty$.

Figure 1: Support of $S_{xy}(f_1, f_2)$ for $\alpha > \beta$ and WSS signal $\{s(t)\}$.

Theorem 3.1 also suggests a natural estimator of the Doppler angle $\tan(\theta_D) = \beta/\alpha$ and the difference $\tau = \tau_2 - \tau_1$ is to coherently integrate $S_{xy}(f_1, f_2)$ over radial lines in the frequency plane weighted with the right phase:

$$G_{xy}(\tau, \theta) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{+i2\pi f \tau} S_{xy}(f \cos(\theta), f \sin(\theta)) df.$$

This "coherent collapse" is a direct generalization of the collapsing techniques of Hurd and Gerr [5] and are illustrated in the simulations. However, it does not seem to admit a ready generalization to PC processes. To see why, we generalize Theorem 3.1 to the case when the signal is PC.

4 Doppler Smoothing

Theorem 4.1 Assume the sensor outputs $\{x(t)\}$ and $\{y(t)\}$ are generated by the linear motion model (LMM). Assume signal $\{s(t)\}$ is both harmonizable and periodically correlated with period T . Assume also $\{s(t)\}$ is uncorrelated with the harmonizable noise processes $\{u(t)\}$ and $\{v(t)\}$. Assume also that both noise processes are jointly uncorrelated. Then the sensor output $\{x(t)\}$ is harmonizable and PC with period $\alpha^{-1}T$. The sensor output $\{y(t)\}$ is harmonizable and PC with period $\beta^{-1}T$. The sensor outputs are **not** jointly PC but have cross spectrum:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{xy}(f_1, f_2) &= \frac{1}{\alpha\beta} e^{-i2\pi\{\alpha^{-1}f_1\tau_1 - \beta^{-1}f_2\tau_2\}} S_{ss}(\alpha^{-1}f_1, \beta^{-1}f_2) \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha\beta} e^{-i2\pi\{\alpha^{-1}f_1\tau_1 - \beta^{-1}f_2\tau_2\}} \\ &\quad \times \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} S_k(\alpha^{-1}f_1) \delta(\alpha^{-1}f_1 - \beta^{-1}f_2 - k/T). \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2 illustrates the spectral support for the cross-spectrum of Theorem 4.1. This figure indicates that the radial smoothing probably would be inappropriate. Indeed, the line through the origin might be estimated properly, but the other lines would likely smear and obscure useful features.

A new estimator is suggested by smoothing the raw cross spectrum using a *fixed* smoothing angle θ :

$$\begin{aligned} S_{xy}^{(D)}(b, \epsilon, \theta; f_1, f_2) &= \int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} S_{xy}(b; f_1 + f \cos(\theta), f_2 + f \sin(\theta)) df \end{aligned}$$

Thus, an estimate of the cross spectrum is generated for each smoothing angle. We will call this estimation procedure “Doppler smoothing”.

When the smoothing angle θ matches the Doppler angle then the lines of support of S_{xy} should be most prominent. When $\theta = 45^\circ$, this estimator is the diagonal smoothing used in Theorem 2.1. Doppler smoothing will properly estimate the spectral support, *provided* that θ matches the Doppler ratio. Since the Doppler ratio is unknown, a search over smoothing angles for a “maximal response” is suggested.

Theorem 4.1 also suggests yet another method for estimating the Doppler ratio for PC signals: note that $\{x(t)\}$ and $\{y(t)\}$ are PC but with periods $\alpha^{-1}T$ and $\beta^{-1}T$, respectively. Thus, the diagonal smoothing of Theorem 2.1 or the collapsing techniques [5] may be employed to obtain these periods. This will also be discussed in the simulations.

5 Simulations

The simulations presented in this section illustrate both the radial and Doppler smoothing techniques. For consistency, all simulations have the following features in common: the sample rate (SR) is set at SR=32 Hertz; the total number of samples $N = 256$

Figure 2: Support of $S_{xy}(f_1, f_2)$ for $\alpha > \beta$ and PC signal $\{s(t)\}$.

which corresponds to an 8-second stretch of data; the signal $\{s(t)\}$ will be Gaussian and have a sample variance $\tilde{\sigma}_s^2$ set to 1; the signal is bandlimited to the frequency interval [3, 12] Hertz; the sensor noises $\{u(t)\}$ and $\{v(t)\}$ are Gaussian and IID with mean 0 and sample variances denoted as $\tilde{\sigma}_u^2$ and $\tilde{\sigma}_v^2$; Signal dilation from a time series was performed using the DFT expansion:

$$s(\alpha t) = \sum_{n=N/2}^{N/2-1} \hat{s}(n) e^{+i2\pi\alpha n t/N},$$

where $\hat{s}(n)$ denotes the n th DFT coefficient of the signal and $t = k/SR$ for $k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$. Time delay was implemented as a “circular shift”:

$$s(t - \tau) = \sum_{n=N/2}^{N/2-1} e^{-i2\pi n \tau/N} \hat{s}(n) e^{+i2\pi n t/N}.$$

Example 5.1 (Radial Smoothing) The signal is a WSS Gaussian time series generated by filtering IID Gaussian noise to the frequency interval [3, 12] Hertz and then normalizing so the sample variance is 1. The Doppler scale for $\{x(t)\}$ is $\alpha = 1$. The Doppler scale for $\{y(t)\}$ is β which was set to correspond to an angle $\theta = 40^\circ$ ($\tan(\theta) = \beta/\alpha$). The time delays were set to zero. The sensor noises $\{u(t)\}$ and $\{v(t)\}$ are IID zero-mean Gaussian with sample variances set to 1.

Figure 3 displays the signal and its dilated version. Figure 4 displays the sensor outputs.

Figure 5 is a contour plot of an estimate of the cross-spectrum obtained by radial smoothing the raw cross-spectrum along the radial angles 30° to 50° in 1° increments. The raw cross-spectrum was formed by taking the FFT of the sensor outputs — no windowing was used at this point. The radial smoothing was performed by a linear convolution of a 16-bin rectangular window along each radial slice of the raw cross-spectrum. For display purposes, a 95% threshold was set using the histogram of this estimate.

The lag-Doppler function G_{xy} was computed using the radially smoothed cross-spectrum. Figure 6 is a contour plot of this function using a 95% threshold obtained from the histogram of this estimate.

Example 5.2 (Doppler Smoothing)

The signal $\{s(t)\}$ is a Gaussian P.C time series generated by filtering IID Gaussian noise to the frequency interval [3, 12] Hertz to produce the time series $\{z(t)\}$, amplitude modulating $\{z(t)\}$ as follows:

$$s(t) = (1 + \cos(2\pi T^{-1}t))z(t),$$

and then normalizing so the sample variance of $\{s(t)\}$ is 1. For this example, we take $T^{-1} = 5$ Hertz. The Doppler scale for $\{x(t)\}$ is $\alpha = 1$. The Doppler scale for $\{y(t)\}$ is β which was set to correspond to an angle $\theta = 40^\circ$ ($\tan(\theta) = \beta/\alpha$). The time delays were set to zero. The sensor noises $\{u(t)\}$ and $\{v(t)\}$ are IID zero-mean Gaussian with sample variances set to 1.

Figure 7 displays the signal and its dilated version. Figure 8 displays the sensor outputs.

Figure 9 plots the spectral coherence [5] and the collapsed coherence of $\{x(t)\}$. The spectral coherence was estimated by diagonally smoothing the raw cross-spectrum of $\{x(t)\}$ using 40 frequency bins which corresponds to smoothing over 5 Hertz. The contour plot of the spectral coherence only displays those features above the 95% threshold, where the threshold is determined using the Goodman test [5]. Note that the coherent collapse is displaying a small spike at $\alpha T^{-1} = 5$ Hertz.

Figure 10 plots the spectral coherence and the collapsed coherence of $\{y(t)\}$. Note that the coherent collapse is displaying a small spike at $\beta T^{-1} = 5 \times .8391 = 4.20$ Hertz.

Figure 11 is a contour plot of an estimate of the cross-spectrum obtained by Doppler smoothing the raw cross-spectrum using the Doppler angle $\theta = 40^\circ$. The raw cross-spectrum was formed by taking the FFT of the sensor outputs — no windowing was used past this point. A 95% threshold was set using the histogram of this estimate.

The lag-Doppler function G_{xy} was computed using this Doppler smoothed cross-spectrum. Figure 12 is a contour plot of this function using a 95% threshold obtained from the histogram of this estimate.

6 Summary

The technique of diagonal smoothing readily adapts to produce cross-spectral estimators for sensor outputs governed by the linear motion model (LMM). In addition, consistent spectral estimation of almost PC processes has been obtained by Hurd and Leskow [6] using this same technique. Thus, it seems reasonable to conjecture that radial and Doppler smoothing estimators will apply to these more general random processes.

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Figure 3: Time series of the signal and its dilated version

Figure 4: Time series of the two sensors: $\tilde{\sigma}_s^2 = \tilde{\sigma}_u^2 = \tilde{\sigma}_v^2 = 1$.

Figure 5: Contour plot of the magnitude of the cross-spectrum obtained by radial smoothing. Only features above the 95% threshold are displayed.

Figure 6: Contour plot of the Lag-Doppler estimate G_{xy} . Only features above the 95% threshold are displayed.

Figure 7: Time series of the PC signal and its dilated version

Figure 8: Time series of the two sensors: $\tilde{\sigma}_s^2 = \tilde{\sigma}_u^2 = \tilde{\sigma}_v^2 = 1$.

Figure 9: On the left is a contour plot of the magnitude of an estimate of the spectral coherence of $\{x(t)\}$. Diagonal smoothing using $L = 40$ frequency bins. Only features above the 95% threshold are displayed. On the right is plot of the collapsed coherence.

Figure 10: On the left is a contour plot of the magnitude of an estimate of the spectral coherence of $\{y(t)\}$ obtained by diagonal smoothing using $L = 40$ frequency bins. Only features above the 95% threshold are displayed. On the right is plot of the collapsed coherence.

Figure 11: Contour plot of the magnitude of an estimate of the cross-spectrum obtained by smoothing at the Doppler angle of $\theta = 40^\circ$ using a 40-bin smoothing window.

Figure 12: Contour plot of the Lag-Doppler estimate G_{xy} . Only features above the 95% threshold are displayed.